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PRAXIS IN TEACHING TLE AND STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT IN JUNIOR HIGH OF PINAMUKAN INTEGRATED SCHOOL

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This study explores the impact of teaching praxis on students' achievement in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) in the junior high of Pinamukan Integrated School, focusing on the effectiveness of various teaching practices and the challenges encountered by teachers. The research was driven by the need to assess whether teachers' methods align with the goals of the K-12 curriculum and Republic Act 10533, which emphasizes enhancing teacher quality to improve student outcomes. Through total population sampling, TLE teachers were selected for the study, offering insights into how they adapt their instructional techniques to meet evolving industry standards, incorporate multidisciplinary approaches, and cater to students with diverse backgrounds and skill levels.

Findings reveal a high level of achievement among students and a significant correlation between teaching practices and student performance. However, teachers face considerable challenges, including limited resources, rapid curriculum shifts, technological integration gaps, varying student competencies, and alignment with industry standards. To address these challenges, the study proposes enrichment activities aimed at refining teaching methods and strengthening professional development programs. The study concludes that improving teaching praxis in TLE is essential to enhancing both teaching performance and student achievement, offering recommendations for local contextualized strategies that support long-term educational success.

Keywords: Praxis in Teaching, Students' Achievement

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